

Heterocyclic Compounds. XII. Colour Tests, Spectra and Reactions of Some Indole Derivatives

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The synthesis of 5-ethoxy-6-methoxyindole and 6-ethoxy-7-methoxyindole is described. Different colour reactions, u.v. spectra and sym-trinitrobenzene derivatives of indoles and their reactions are also described.

In the course of our work on some indole alkaloids, it became necessary to study the different colour reactions and the u.v. spectra of various indole derivatives. Whilst some of these data are described in literature it was thought worthwhile to have them at one place for a comparative study.

With the above object in view the colour reactions of different indoles with various reagents and their u.v. spectra were studied and are described in Tables I and II.

Sym-trinitrobenzene derivatives of some of the indoles have also been prepared which could be used for their characterisation. The general method consists of the addition of a hot alcoholic solution of the reagent to an alcoholic solution of the indole. The derivatives usually separated on cooling and were crystallised from alcohol and are listed in Table III.

The present paper also describes the synthesis of two new indoles, namely, 5-ethoxy-6-methoxyindole and 6-ethoxy-7-methoxyindole.

5-Ethoxy-6-methoxyindole was synthesised from isovanillin which on ethylation gave 3-ethoxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde¹. The latter was treated with nitromethane in acetic acid in the presence of sodium acetate to give 3-ethoxy-4-methoxy- β -nitrostyrene¹. Nitration under careful cooling with fuming nitric acid yielded 6, β -dinitro-3-ethoxy-4-methoxystyrene which on hydrogenation with 5% Pd/C afforded 5-ethoxy-6-methoxyindole in 25% yield.

A similar method was adopted for the synthesis of 6-ethoxy-7-methoxyindole. Vanillin was nitrated with fuming nitric acid to 2-nitrovanillin² which on ethylation gave 4-ethoxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrobenzaldehyde³. The latter with nitromethane in acetic acid afforded 2, β -dinitro-4-ethoxy-3-methoxystyrene which was hydrogenated with 5% Pd/C to 6-ethoxy-7-methoxyindole.

1. S. R. Agrawal, M.Sc. Thesis, University of Bombay, 1962, p. 91.
2. F. Tieman and N. Nagai, *Ber.*, 1878, **11**, 647.
3. E. Spath and K. Tharrer, *Ber.*, 1933, **66**, 911.

Preliminary pharmacological investigations have shown that benzyloxytryptamines and hydroxytryptamines are responsible for the vasoconstriction properties of serum⁴. In view of these properties several unsuccessful attempts were made to synthesise 6-benzyloxy-5-methoxyindole, 6-benzyloxy-7-methoxyindole and 5-benzyloxy-6-methoxyindole. In all cases the required dinitrostyrene derivatives were obtained but attempts to reduce them with iron and acetic acid or by catalytic hydrogenation led to the formation of pastes from which the required indoles could not be isolated. The failure to prepare the benzyloxyindoles could be due to debenylation during reduction giving rise to hydroxyindoles some of which are known to be unstable⁵. Accordingly, the pastes obtained above were boiled with

TABLE I
Colour reactions of some indole derivatives

Indole derivatives	HCl/vanillin	HNO ₃	Ehrlich's reagent	Ce(IV)/ Ce(SO ₄) ₂
Indole*	Orange red	brick red	pink (imm.)	brown
2,3-Dihydroindole ⁷	red	brown	pink (imm.)	brown
2-Methylindole ⁸	yellow	faint yellow	pink (imm.)	brown
2-Methylindoline ⁹	crimson red	yellow	pink (imm.)	brown
2-Phenylindole ¹⁰	rose	yellow	pinkish purple (imm.)	grey green
N-Methylindole ¹¹	red	deep brown red	pink (imm.)	brown
N-Methylindoline ⁹	orange red	brick red	pink (imm.)	brown
Skatole*	dark pink	yellow	pink (imm.)	red orange
Indole-3-aldehyde*	light pink (hot)	yellow	pink (2-3 hours)	orange
Indole-3-acetic acid*	pink	brown	pink (15 minutes)	orange
4,5-Dimethoxyindole ¹²	dark red to violet	violet	pinkish purple (imm.)	violet
5,6-Dimethoxyindole ¹³	pink	light brown	light pink (15 minutes)	green
6,7-Dimethoxyindole ¹⁴	crimson red	brown red	pinkish purple (imm.)	brown
5-Ethoxy-6-methoxyindole	brown red	light brown	pinkish purple (imm.)	cream
6-Ethoxy-7-methoxyindole	crimson red	brown red	pinkish purple (½ hour)	brown red
Norharman ¹⁵	—	yellow	—	—
Harman ¹⁶	—	yellow	—	—
Carbazole*	purple	light green	blue to purple (½ hour)	green

* Bought from market and purified by crystallisation from dilute alcohol followed by sublimation under vacuum.

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TABLE II

U.V. absorption spectra of indole derivatives

Indole derivatives	λ_{max} (m μ)	log ϵ
Indole	222, 282	4.05, 3.76
2, 3-Dihydroindole	220, 245, 280	3.98, 3.48, 3.51
2-Methylindole	225, 275	4.13, 3.79
2-Methylindoline	242, 292	4.05, 3.64
2-Phenylindole	214, 238, 310	4.19, 4.10, 4.24
Skatole	227, 282	4.13, 3.73
4,5-Dimethoxyindole	220, 270	4.33, 3.78
5,6-Dimethoxyindole	220, 265, 270, 302	4.06, 3.38, 3.40, 3.57
6,7-Dimethoxyindole	226, 270	4.23, 3.80
5-Ethoxy-6-methoxyindole	225, 273, 300	4.32, 3.61, 3.82
6-Ethoxy-7-methoxyindole	222, 270	4.22, 3.79
Harman	239, 288, 335, 349	4.28, 3.93, 3.27, 3.27
Norharman	214, 289, 315, 339, 351	3.92, 3.80, 2.99, 3.19, 3.22
Carbazole	234, 256, 293, 325, 337	4.42, 4.16, 4.10, 3.44, 3.39

TABLE III

No.	Trinitrobenzene adducts of	M.P. °C	Colour and crystalline Form	Mol. Formula	Analysis		N%
					Calcd.	Found	
1.	Dihydroindole	185-86	orange needles	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₆	16.86	16.7	16.7
2.	2-Methylindoline	152-55	light yellow needles	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₆	16.18	16.3	16.3
3.	N-Methylindoline	132-33	brick red needles.	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₆	16.18	16.4	16.4
4.	4,5-Dimethoxyindole	113	brick red needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₈	14.36	14.0	14.0
5.	5,6-Dimethoxyindole	159-60	dark orange needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₈	14.36	14.1	14.1
6.	6,7-Dimethoxyindole	117-18	brick red needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₈	14.36	14.2	14.2
7.	5-Ethoxy-6-Methoxyindole	134	brick red needles	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₈	13.86	13.6	13.6
8.	6-Ethoxy-7-Methoxyindole	132	crimson red needles	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₈	13.86	13.6	13.6
9.	Norharman	160-61	yellow needles	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₆	18.37	17.9	17.9
10.	Harman	124-25	yellow needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₆	18.11	18.6	18.6

benzylchloride in acetone solution in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate. In these cases also no pure products could be isolated.

With a view to develop an easy method for preparation of some tryptamine derivatives required for another project, different indoles were condensed with substituted β -nitrostyrenes to give adducts of the general structure I and are given in Table IV. The general method consists in heating equimolar quantities of the two reactants on a water bath for about 5 hr.

With some indoles, the addition products were formed by heating them with the β -nitrostyrenes over a free flame for about 5 mins.

Attempts to obtain adducts of indole with other dienophiles such as crotonaldehyde, crotonic acid, cinnamic acid and acetylene-dimethyl-dicarboxylate were unsuccessful.

Desired adducts of the general structure II were also obtained by the reaction of indoles with various chalcones in about 50-60% yields. The reaction was carried out in the presence of acetic acid and acetic anhydride. The same chalcones were also obtained in the presence of sodium methoxide. Some of the compounds obtained were further characterised by the preparation of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones. The different indoles and the chalcones used for the condensation are given in Table V.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of 6, β -dinitro-3-ethoxy-4-methoxystyrene : To a well stirred solution of 3-ethoxy-4-methoxy- β -nitrostyrene (4 g.) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml.) was added fuming nitric acid (d. 1.5) (15 ml.) dropwise keeping the temperature below 0° and stirred for a further 2 hr. at the same temperature. Dilution of the mixture with cold water gave a

TABLE IV

Indole	β -Nitro-styrene	Adduct			M.P. °C	Analysis			
		R	R ₁	R ₂		C	H	H	
Indole	2,3-dimethoxy-	H	H	2',3'-OCH ₃	138-39	66.3	5.5	66.2	5.4
-do-	4-methoxy	H	H	4'-OCH ₃	149-50	68.9	5.4	68.8	5.2
2-Methylindole	2,3-dimethoxy-	H	CH ₃	2',3'-OCH ₃	174-75	67.0	5.9	66.7	6.3
-do-	4-methoxy-	H	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	119-20	69.7	5.8	69.7	5.9
-do-	2,3,4-trimethoxy-	H	CH ₃	2',3',4'-OCH ₃	148-49	64.8	5.9	64.6	6.2
2-Phenylindole	2,3-dimethoxy-	H	C ₆ H ₅	2',3'-OCH ₃	173	71.6	5.6	71.5	5.6
-do-	4-methoxy-	H	C ₆ H ₅	4'-OCH ₃	155-57	74.2	5.4	74.3	5.8
N-Methylindole	2,3-dimethoxy-	CH ₃	H	2',3'-OCH ₃	138	67.0	5.9	67.2	5.9
2-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-indole ^s	2,3-dimethoxy-	H	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	2',3'-OCH ₃ *	200	69.4	5.6	69.4	5.4
-do-	3,4-dimethoxy-	H	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	3',4'-OCH ₃	180-81	69.4	5.6	69.3	5.2
-do-	4-methoxy-	H	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	4'-OCH ₃	150	76.6	5.5	76.7	5.5
-do-	2,3,4-trimethoxy-	H	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	2',3',4'-OCH ₃	179-80	67.9	5.6	68.3	5.2

* Crystallised from ethyl acetate. All other adducts crystallised from alcohol.

6. K. Kaji and H. Negashima, *J. Pharm. Soc. (Japan)*, 1952, **72**, 1589; *C.A.*, 1953, **47**, 9318.

TABLE V

Indole	Chalkone	Adduct			Solvent and shape*	M.P. °C	Analysis Found			2,4-DNP M.P.	Solvent	Analysis	
		R	R ₁	R ₂			R ₃	Reqd. C	Reqd. H			Reqd. N	Found C
Indole	2,4'-dimethyl	H	H	2-CH ₃	A	164	85.0	6.5	84.7	6.7			
2-Methylindole	-do-	H	CH ₃	2-CH ₃	A	137	85.0	6.8	85.1	6.7	237-39	A	12.8 12.5
2-Phenylindole	-do-	H	C ₆ H ₅	2-CH ₃	A	213	86.7	6.3	86.3	6.2			
N-Methylindole	-do-	CH ₃	H	2-CH ₃	A	171	85.0	6.8	84.9	6.8	237-39	C	12.8 12.7
Indole	4-methoxy-4'-methyl	H	H	4-OCH ₃	A	172	81.0	6.2	80.7	6.0			
2-Methylindole	-do-	H	CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	A	163	81.5	6.5	81.8	6.9			
2-Phenylindole	-do-	H	C ₆ H ₅	4-OCH ₃	A	186	83.6	6.1	83.3	6.5			
N-Methylindole	-do-	CH ₃	H	4-OCH ₃	A	158	81.5	6.5	81.2	6.5	231	A	12.4 12.3
Indole	4,4'-dimethoxy	H	H	4-OCH	A	155	77.9	6.0	77.9	6.3			
2-Methylindole	-do-	H	CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	light yellow needles A	172	78.2	6.3	78.2	6.6	136-38	A	12.0 11.6
N-Methylindole	-do-	CH ₃	H	4-OCH ₃	A	168	78.2	6.3	78.5	6.5			
Indole	2-methyl-4'-methoxy	H	H	2-CH ₃	A	185	81.0	6.2	81.1	6.2			
2-Methylindole	-do-	H	CH ₃	2-CH ₃	A	171	81.5	6.5	81.4	6.7			
N-Methylindole	-do-	CH ₃	H	2-CH ₃	B	213	81.5	6.5	81.4	6.9			
Indole	benzalacetophenone	H	H	H	D-E	140	84.9	5.8	84.8	5.4	207-08	A	13.9 14.2
2-Methylindole	-do-	H	CH ₃	H	prisms						213	C	13.5 13.6
N-Methylindole	-do-	CH ₃	H	H	oil	175	85.0	6.2	84.9	6.0			
2-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-indole	-do-	H	4-OCH ₃	H	C								
Indole	4-methoxy	H	C ₆ H ₄	H	oil						247	C	11.5 11.6
2-Methylindole	-do-	H	H	4-OCH ₃	D	162	81.1	5.9	81.1	5.8	218	C	12.7 12.9
2-Phenylindole	-do-	H	CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	oil						216	C	12.7 12.5
N-Methylindole	-do-	H	C ₆ H ₅	4-OCH ₃	oil						212-13	C	13.1 12.8
Indole	4-methoxy	CH ₃	H	4-OCH ₃	C-F	127-28	81.3	6.2	80.9	6.1	193	C	12.7 13.0
2-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-indole	-do-	H	4-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃	yellow needles								
			C ₆ H ₄	H	oil	220						C	10.9 11.3

* All compounds obtained as colourless needles except where mentioned otherwise.

Solvents: A, alcohol; B, ethyl acetate; C, acetic acid; D, chloroform; E, light petroleum; F, water.

yellow solid (2.8 g.) which was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 188°. (Found N, 10.5; $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O_6$ requires N, 10.5%).

Preparation of 5-ethoxy-6-methoxyindole: To a solution of the above dinitrostyrene (2 g.) in a mixture of ethyl acetate (20 ml.), alcohol (2 ml.) and acetic acid (2.5 ml.) was added 5% Pd/C (200 mg.) and hydrogenated at 45 p.s.i. for 3 hr. The catalyst was removed by filtration and the filtrate extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution dried and concentrated to a small bulk. Addition of petrol ether (40–60°) (25 ml.) gave a brownish solid which was sublimed under vacuum to give 5-ethoxy-6-methoxyindole (300 mg.). It was recrystallised from dilute alcohol as needles, m.p. 134° (Found C, 69.1; H, 7.1. $C_{11}H_{13}NO_2$ requires C, 69.1; H, 6.8%).

Preparation of 2,β-dinitro-4-ethoxy-3-methoxystyrene: A mixture of 4-ethoxy-3-methoxy-2-nitrobenzaldehyde (5 g.), nitromethane (3 g.), ammonium acetate (2 g.) and glacial acetic acid (20 ml.) was refluxed for 2 hr. at 130°. The yellow solid which separated on cooling was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 117–18° (Found N, 11.0. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O_6$ requires N, 10.5%).

Preparation of 6-ethoxy-7-methoxyindole: The dinitrostyrene (2 g.) was hydrogenated as above to give 6-ethoxy-7-methoxyindole (315 mg.) crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 70°. (Found C, 68.9; H, 6.9. $C_{11}H_{13}NO_2$ requires C, 69.1; H, 6.8%).

Preparation of β-nitrostyrene adducts: Equimolar amounts of the indole derivative and substituted β-nitrostyrene were heated on a water bath for about 5 hr. The progress of the reaction was generally indicated by a darkening of the oily mixture which usually solidified on keeping overnight when the solid could be crystallised from alcohol. See Table IV.

Preparation of 3-(p-methoxyphenyl)-4'-methyl-3-(2-methyl-3-indolyl)-propiophenone: To a mixture of 2-methylindole (1.3 g.) and 4-methoxy-4'-methylchalcone (2.5 g.) was added acetic acid (6 ml.) and acetic anhydride (2 ml.). After heating for 24 hr. on a water bath, the reaction mixture was poured into water (100 ml.) to give 2.02 g. of the adduct. See Table V (i.r. 3330-NH, 1670-CO, 1515-OCH₃, 1470-CH₂CO).

Preparation of 3-(p-methoxyphenyl)-4'-methyl-3-(1-methyl-3-indolyl)-propiophenone: A mixture of N-methylindole and 4-methoxy-4-methylindole was reacted as above to give the desired adduct. See Table V (i.r. 1670-CO, 1515-OCH₃, 1470-CH₂CO, 1300 N-methylindole.)

The authors thank Mr. R. S. Kulkarni for the microanalyses.

